

Research article

Parasitism and fluctuating asymmetry in *Liolaemus darwini* (Squamata: Liolaemidae) from Argentina

Gabriel N. Castillo^{1,2}, Cynthia J. González-Rivas^{3,4}

(1) [Corresponding author] Parasitología en animales silvestre, Departamento de Biología, Facultad de Ciencias Exactas, Físicas y Naturales, Universidad Nacional de San Juan, San Juan, Argentina, nataliocastillo@gmail.com

(2) CONICET (Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas), San Juan, Argentina

(3) Parasitología en animales silvestre, Departamento de Biología, Facultad de Ciencias Exactas, Físicas y Naturales, Universidad Nacional de San Juan, San Juan, Argentina

(4) Centro de Rehabilitación de Fauna Silvestre, Educación Ambiental y Recreación Responsable, San Juan, Argentina, cynthiajesica.gr@gmail.com

Abstract: A comparative analysis and investigation of the relationship between the parasite *Physaloptera retusa* (Physalopterae) and the fluctuating asymmetry (FA) of the lizard *Liolaemus darwini* from Argentina was carried out. In this study, the effect produced by the presence of *P. retusa* on the symmetry of the heads of lizards has been investigated. Thirty specimens (12 parasitised and 18 non-parasitised) from a population of *L. darwini* were examined. The results obtained showed statistical differences in fluctuating asymmetry between parasitised and non-parasitised specimens; the parasitised *L. darwini* specimens presented greater head asymmetry compared to the non-parasitised ones, confirming the initial hypothesis. The present study allowed us to consider the analysis of fluctuating asymmetry as a tool that, together with parasites, can be considered and be useful in studies related to reptile populations and in conservation biology.

Keywords: conservation, geometric morphometry, Nematoda, parasitism, *Physaloptera retusa*

Introduction

Parasites are one of the most common and successful forms of life within the animal kingdom (Poulin & Morand, 2000; Lucius et al., 2018), where it is estimated that more than 50% of living beings are parasites or have some form of parasitic life (Lucius et al., 2018). Therefore, studies on helminths that parasitise wild animals generate information that allows us to understand the biology and ecology of their hosts (Vieira et al., 2016). From the point of view of the vertebrate host, these studies are important in conservation biology, because severe parasitosis could compromise the host, causing decreased defences and greater susceptibility to diseases (Spinelli et al., 1992).

Nematodes of the genus *Physaloptera* Rudolphi, 1819 (Physalopterae) include 105 parasitic species of reptiles, amphibians, birds and mammals. In reptiles, they are located in the stomach (Pereira et al.,

2012, 2014). In the Neotropics, approximately eight species of *Physaloptera* are recorded, of which four species are recorded in Argentina: *P. retusa* Rudolphi, 1819, *P. lutzi* Cristoófaró, Guimarães and Rodrigues, 1976, *P. liophis* Vicente and Santos, 1974 and *P. tupinambae* Pereira, Alves, Rocha, Lima and Luque, 2012 parasitising reptiles of the families Liolaemidae, Tropiduridae, Leiosauridae and Dipsadidae. The majority of records correspond to *P. retusa* and *P. lutzi* in *Liolaemus* spp. (Castillo et al., 2020). *P. retusa* nematodes adhered to the stomach mucosa have been reported to cause erosive inflammatory foci (Goldberg & Bursey, 1989).

Liolaemus darwini Bell, 1843 is a species of lizard with sexual dimorphism and wide distribution in Argentina, inhabiting mainly desert environments (Cei, 1986; Acosta et al., 2017). They are oviparous with two lays per year, with an average litter size between three and six eggs (Cei, 1986; Acosta et al., 2017). It is a mainly insectivorous species, spe-

Fig. 1. The Encón study area, 25 de Mayo District, San Juan Province, Argentina.

cialised in ants (Cei, 1986). Currently, its conservation status is Not Threatened (NT) (Abdala et al., 2012).

Fluctuating asymmetry (FA) is the random deviation between the right and left sides of a bilateral symmetry plan in a population of organisms (Graham et al., 2010). Currently, it is used in reptiles as a tool to understand the effects of stress on the development of ecological communities (Sarre, 1996; Tull & Brusard, 2007; Lazić et al., 2013, 2016; Castillo & González-Rivas, 2023). Several studies have indicated that the main sources of stress that induce fluctuating asymmetry in reptile populations are due to human disturbances (Castillo & González-Rivas, 2023) which, together with genetic changes (Clarke, 1995; Vervust et al., 2008), are sources of the main phenotypic variations (Castillo & González-Rivas, 2023). However, extreme temperatures, lack of food, presence of predators and parasitism are also important sources of phenotypic variation and influence fluctuating asymmetry (Bonn et al., 1996; Sasal & Pampoulie, 2000; Brown & Brown, 2002; Pečínková et al., 2007; Tatalović et al., 2020). There is evidence for a relationship between parasites and fluctuating asymmetry, which shows that different levels of asymmetry in a population may be due to a strong ex-

posure to parasites. The mechanism by which parasitism induces different levels of asymmetry is unknown, however it is likely due to nutritional stress generated by the parasites (Bonn et al., 1996; Brown & Brown, 2002).

Thus, parasitism favours phenotypic variation, which results in greater fluctuating asymmetry (Sasal & Pampoulie, 2000; Brown & Brown, 2002). Similarly, asymmetry and parasitism could indirectly lead to a reduction in reproductive success in parasitised males (Sasal & Pampoulie, 2000). Because of this, it is possible to assume that parasite load is a measure of stress (Bonn et al., 1996).

In this study, the effect of *P. retusa* on the symmetry of the cephalic region of lizards was investigated due to its importance in ecological processes. To do so, a population of *L. darwini* was compared with parasitised and non-parasitised specimens. It was assumed that the environmental conditions were the same and the only variation was the presence and absence of parasites. The purpose of this article is to demonstrate for the first time in Argentina that there is a statistically significant relationship between the levels of fluctuating asymmetry in the head of the lizard *L. darwini* and the presence of parasites.

Fig. 2. (A) Cephalic region of *Liolaemus darwini*, (B) configuration of landmarks.

Materials and methods

The study area is located in the town of El Encón (Fig. 1), 25 de Mayo District (32°12'56" S, 67°47'43" W), Province of San Juan, Argentina. This area is represented by the Monte phytogeographic province, that comprises vast arid areas with average precipitation < 100 mm/year. The Monte sector covers an area of 40,499 km², corresponding to 45% of the province's total. Xerophilous plants, adapted to the warm dry climate with little summer precipitation, are predominant. The vegetation is characterised by the presence of bushes exceeding 3 m in height (Morello, 1958).

Sampling was carried out in December 2019. Eight pitfall traps (width 25 cm, height 37 cm) were placed randomly. Each trap was buried 37 cm deep, leaving the trap entrance opening at ground level. Every 4 days the traps were checked and the individuals that had fallen into them were removed. A total of n= 30 adult specimens of *L. darwini* were captured, of which n= 12 individuals were parasitised and n= 18 were not parasitised.

The captured specimens were taken to the laboratory. Each individual was sacrificed by intraperitoneal injection of euthanasia solution, Euthanyle® (sodium pentobarbital), fixed in Bouin's solution for 24 hours, labeled and preserved in 70% ethyl alcohol. The spec-

imens of *L. darwini* studied are deposited in the Herpetological Collection, Biology Department, School of Exact, Physical, and Natural Sciences, National University of San Juan, Argentina (*L. darwini*: UNSJ: 4033–4052). Subsequently, the individuals were dissected for the extraction of nematodes through a longitudinal ventral mouth-anus incision. The digestive tract was removed and examined using a binocular stereoscopic microscope. The nematodes found were preserved in ethanol 70°. Nematodes were cleared in lactophenol and examined via light microscope and relevant bibliography were used to identify the parasite (Ramallo & Díaz, 1998; Anderson et al., 2009). The nematodes studied are deposited in the Parasitological Collection, Biology Department, Faculty of Exact, Physical and Natural Sciences, National University of San Juan, Argentina (*Physaloptera retusa*: UNSJPar: 260).

The head region of *L. darwini* adults was analysed (Fig. 2). High-resolution photos of all specimens were taken with a Nikon® COOLPIX P520 42X digital camera. The camera was placed on a tripod with the same focal length height (40 cm) in each photograph. The dorsal view of each lizard's head was captured with a millimetre grid to record scale. A level was used to maintain adequate horizontality of the camera. In *L. darwini* specimens, 10 Type 1 land-

Fig. 3. Cross-validation scores. Frequencies observed for *Liolaemus darwini* in parasitized and no parasitized. Fisher's discriminant rule (x-axis) with a cut-off point at zero; parasitised with positive values, non-parasitised with negative values.

marks were established in scales of the cephalic region. In all cases, only adult specimens were used.

For the selection of landmarks, the standard protocol of Aguirre & Prado (2018) and Toro-Ibacache et al. (2010) was followed, taking into account homology, coverage, repeatability, consistency in relative position and coplanarity. Photos were taken at the same time that the euthanasia occurred, thus avoiding captures of folded or dehydrated samples as a result of poor preservation of specimens. To avoid accuracy error, all photographic montages were made by the same person. Landmarks 1 and 2 corresponded to the middle region of the head. Landmarks 3, 5, 7 and 9 were from the right region and landmarks 4, 6, 8, and 10 were from the left region of the head.

For the construction of files and digitisation of photos, the programs tpsUtil version 1.74 and tpsDig 2.3 were used. Using the tpsRelw program version 1.69, the consensus shapes that correspond to the average shapes of all the shapes subject to analysis are determined. In addition, partial and relative warps were graphed. A generalised procrustean analysis was performed by using MorphoJ v. 1.06 (Klingenberg, 2011). This allowed the removal of variation components from specimens (in images) that did not correspond to the shape. Additionally, an outliers test was performed to check for individual specimens that deviated strongly from the average. The consensual landmarks were graphed. Covariance matrices were generated. "Wireframes" were created allowing a set of connected lines to be formed between the reference landmarks.

Size data was retained as centroid size (CS). Shape differences were visualised with deformation

grids. To explore variations in size, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed, with the logarithm of the centroid size as the dependent variable and the parasitised and non-parasitised condition as the independent variable. For a better visualisation of the results, a box-plot analysis was performed with the centroid size.

For the analysis of fluctuating asymmetry in *L. darwini*, "object symmetry" was considered comparing the right sector with the left (Fig. 2). Object symmetry is when the object of interest is itself symmetrical (Klingenberg, 2015). The variation between parasitised and non-parasitised specimens was performed using the "shape FA scores" values. It should be noted that to reduce measurement error, all measurements were repeated twice.

Results

Liolaemus darwini is parasitised by *P. retusa*. In total, 12 parasitised and 18 non-parasitised individuals were recorded. The values of the parasitic ecological indices are: prevalence = 40%; mean intensity = 1.58 and mean abundance = 0.63 ± 0.85 (1-2).

The analyses of shape and size, considering the effects of the parasitised and non-parasitised conditions, showed no statistical differences in size (centroid size) (ANOVA, Procrustes $F= 0.38$; $p= 0.5$) or shape (ANOVA, Procrustes $F= 0.35$; $p= 0.9$) (Table 1 and 2). Figure 3 shows the frequency of the discriminant function scores, a graph corresponding to the cross-validation. Note that the parasitised correspond to the left side and the non-parasitised to the right

Table 1. Procrustes analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the variation in sizes between conditions (parasitised/non-parasitised). “Individual” is the variation of forms between individuals. “Error” corresponds to measurement error. The sums of squares (SS) and mean squares (MS) are in units of Procrustes distances (dimensionless). (df) degrees of liberty, (F) dispersion value and (P) statistical significance value are observed.

Centroid size, Procrustes ANOVA: <i>L. darwini</i>					
Effect	SS	MS	df	F	p
Condition (Parasitised/not parasitised)	0.89	0.89	1	0.38	0.5
Individual	63.11	2.3	27	698.58	0.0001
Error	0.10	0.003	30		

Table 2. Procrustes analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the analysis of developmental instability (fluctuating asymmetry) in *L. darwini* between conditions (parasitised/non-parasitised). Individual, is the variation of shapes between individuals. Directional asymmetry (side), fluctuating asymmetry (Ind* Side). Error, corresponds to the measurement error. Sums of squares (SS) and mean squares (MS) are in units of Procrustes distances (dimensionless). (df) degrees of liberty, (F) dispersion value and (P) statistical significance value are observed.

Shape, Procrustes ANOVA: <i>L. darwini</i>					
Effect	SS	MS	df	F	p
Condition (Parasitised/not parasitised)	0.004	0.00052	8	0.35	0.9
Individual	0.32	0.001	216	4.62	0.0001
Directional asymmetry (Side)	0.01	0.001	8	5.97	0.0001
Fluctuating asymmetry (Ind * Side)	0.07	0.0003	232	25.7	0.0001
Error	0.006	0.00001	480		

Fig. 4. Fluctuating asymmetry values for parasitized and no parasitized hosts.

side, however, there is no substantial separation between parasitised and non-parasitised based on body shape. Therefore, there is an overlap indicating a lack of differences in shapes.

The values of fluctuating asymmetry (specimen/side) were different between parasitised and non-parasitised individuals, showing higher values in the parasitised specimens (ANOVA, Procrustes $F = 25.7$; $p = 0.0001$) (Fig. 4) (Table 2).

Discussion

Information on parasites and fluctuating asymmetry analyses in Argentine reptiles is scarce. Regarding parasites, the few existing parasitological studies on Argentine reptiles are taxonomic (Castillo et al., 2020), especially of widely distributed species such as the genera *Liolaemus* and *Phymaturus* (Castillo et al., 2018; Castillo & Acosta, 2019). Regarding research on fluctuating asymmetry in relation to environmental disturbances in Argentina, so far, only one study by Castillo & González-Rivas (2023) has been carried out in *Aurivela longicauda* (Teiidae).

In the present study we analysed morphological parameters of the lizard *L. darwini* (size, shape and FA of the dorsal region of the head) and Quantitative descriptors of the *P. retusa* population (prevalence, intensity and mean abundance). The purpose of this study is to investigate whether there is a statistically significant association between fluctuating asymmetry levels and the presence of parasites. Overall, we endorse on a limited basis, as did previous researchers (Tatalović et al., 2020), for the idea that FA represents an index of individual quality. These types of analyses are relevant for a more integrated estimation of the ecological status of populations and help to understand the consequences at the community level (Almeida et al., 2023).

We selected the size, shape and symmetry of the head of *L. darwini* as the main trait of analysis, because this is a functional trait that can reflect habitat quality (Anđelković et al., 2023), food availability (Vincent & Herrel, 2007) and competition for a resource such as territoriality or mating (sexual selection) (Valdecantos & Lobo, 2007; Valdez, 2013). When the circumstances of reptile populations are good (free of parasites), individuals are expected to have better body conditions or symmetrical body structures such as the head (Castillo et al., 2023).

The results of the present work seem to indicate a possible effect of the parasites on the host *L. darwini*. Sasal & Pampoulie (2000) mention that the asymmetry in development may be the result of the phenotypic change induced by the parasite. Head asymmetry in *L. darwini* may influence ecological performance. Due to this, presenting symmetrical body structures or good body conditions leads to greater success in sexual selection and obtaining resources than those who are parasitised (suboptimal conditions), because parasites reflect stress in development (Sasal & Pampoulie, 2000; Pojas & Tabugo, 2015). According to these hypotheses, females choose symmetrical mates, because symmetry somehow reflects a hereditary male quality that could affect the viability of offspring (Polak, 1994).

The results of the Procrustes ANOVA indicated random differences (fluctuating asymmetry) between parasitised and non-parasitised populations. This would demonstrate that the presence of *P. retusa* nematodes is associated with notably higher levels of head asymmetry in *L. darwini* lizards. However, apparently the nematodes only affect the normal development of the dorsal region of the head of *L.*

darwini (generating asymmetries), since there was no significant effect regarding head size and shape. The parasitised and non-parasitised populations of *L. darwini* were collected from the same site and under the same environmental conditions. Due to this, no differences in size and shape were recorded, since it is considered that size variations are a product of different environmental conditions, and shapes reflect genetic variations (Clarke, 1995; Vervust et al., 2008).

A possible explanation for the presence of FA in the dorsal region of the head of *L. darwini* is that these parasitised lizards have been exposed to high levels of stress, mainly nutritional, as a result of the damage of the nematodes that are attached to the mucosa of the stomach causing erosive inflammatory foci (Goldberg & Bursey, 1989). In accordance with what was expressed above, there is an integrative nature of the parasite-host association that includes metabolic effects of parasitism and physiological manifestation of the infection in relation to the nutritional physiology of the host. In most host-parasite relationships, the host provides nutrition to the parasite and, in turn, makes its own physiological adjustments and/or alters itself metabolically. These adjustments (mild to severe) include depressed growth, altered food intake, digestive malfunction, and changes in food assimilation (Thompson, 1982). We suggest that the population that is not parasitised and with a low level of FA probably has greater resistance against parasites and, therefore, better genetic quality.

In addition to the present study on *L. darwini*, there are well-documented situations in the literature in which parasites induce or increase fluctuating asymmetry in fish (Sasal & Pampoulie, 2000; Pojas & Tabugo, 2015), insects (Polak, 1994; Bonn et al., 1996) and birds (Brown & Brown, 2002). At times, this has generally been interpreted as a direct consequence of the stress and nutritional deficiency caused by parasites by generating physiological and metabolic changes in the host (Polak, 1994).

In the present study, the prevalence, intensity and mean abundance of *P. retusa* in *L. darwini* is comparable to that previously observed for other Liolaemidae reptiles from Argentina (Castillo et al., 2020). It is known for other host groups that nematode parasites compete with their hosts for nutrients, thus affecting biochemical processes, altering development and inducing FA (Polak, 1994).

Conclusions

As expected, lower FA was observed in the non-parasitised population, indicating that FA analysis is an optimal method for assessing environmental stress. Furthermore, it shows that parasites are one of the possible variables that correlate with reptile symmetry. The results of the present study support the hypothesis that parasitic infection of *P. retusa* during the development of the host *L. darwini* results in an increase in its developmental instability and, therefore, in FA.

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